

SOCIAL CATEGORIZATION

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Abstract

Social categorization is the process by which individuals classify themselves and others into different social groups based on common characteristics such as age, gender, race, ethnicity, occupation or nationality. This categorization can affect attitudes and behavior toward individuals or groups and it often plays an important role in social interactions and dynamics. Many factors influence the social stratification of society. These factors are nothing but conditions that encourage people to discriminate against each other. Even today, remnants of the old caste system still remain in the minds of our people. There still people who think they belong to such clans as “Kipchak”, “Mangit”, or “Kungiro” claiming the titles of “Khoja”, “Eshan”, or “Tora”. Since the beginning society, there has been stratification. During the period of natural stratification, not only tribes, but also the society of countries that have risen in the centers of civilization, such as the Middle East, Egypt, Southern Europe, India and China are stratified according to this principles.

Keywords: social categorization, society, people inequality between, gender inequality, castes, slavery.

With the emergence of society, man first encountered inequality between people. Stratification remains an inevitable fact at all stages of the development of civilization. However, the division of people exists in all groups and associations. Division into social groups can occur according to various criteria: income, access to power, prestigious profession, age, individual characteristics of a person, etc. However, inequality between people is very conditional, because a person wants to

be able to move from one social group to another, thereby improving the quality of life, having access to all benefits. This article raises the problem of social stratification in society. Also, the article discusses various criteria for dividing society, defines the concept of "stratification". Nature initially created inequality between people. People are physically, musically, has creative skills and abilities. Everyone is good at a certain field of activity the closest, in which it reveals its potential to the maximum. Pietro Pomponazzi is like that said: "Every man cannot have equal perfection, but he is great, the second and less. If you eliminate this inequality, the human race will perish or will be deprived of perfection". Since ancient times, people have been searching for food, shelter and fought for the resources they needed to survive. Naturally, the distribution of all benefits was not equal. Most of them are concentrated in hands that are strong, agile and have certain privileges. "Equality is the law of nature. Nature has made nothing equal. Her highest law is submission and dependence." Differentiation is related to it means there are cases. Thus, for example, the ability to fully satisfy one's needs due to restrictions on access to the necessary benefits can lead to negative changes in a person's behavior. He will be cruel, secretive, greedy. According to Gabriel Mable, inequality discriminates people and causes discord and hatred between them causes. ^[1]

Some manifestations of some symptoms of stratification are found in many nations. We can also take India as a bright example. India embodies the most vivid example of the caste system. The term "caste" means "seed", "people", "quality" in Portuguese. This word spread to European languages after the Portuguese came to India in the 16th century and got acquainted with the Indian social system. Many consider the caste system unique to India. This is why the caste system is well developed and has been preserved for a long time in India. Thus, with this name, they began to call groups separated from each other in Indian society. In India, such a class of people is called by the Sanskrit term "jati". In ancient Indian society, before the emergence of a class society at the same time as

"jati", an ancient legalized and perfected system of society - "varna" - castes appeared. Gradually, the varnas (Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas, Shudras) separated from each other. Varnas resembled castes in form. Actually, caste and varna were different from each other. In ancient India, caste was a division of people by occupation, trade or profession, and varna was a division of the population into four classes in that society. People of each caste lived separately from other castes. Any relationship or communication between them was strictly prohibited. Establishing kinship ties between one caste and another was strictly prohibited. Thus, each varna represents a color: Brahmin - white, Kshatriya - red, Vaishya - yellow and Shudra - black. [3] Many legends say that the four varnas originated from the first man, Nurupa. According to the hymn Nurushakasta, Brahmins were born from the mouth of Purusha, the hand of Kshatriyas, the thighs of Vaishyas, and the feet of Shudras. Brahmins were considered the highest varna. Brahmins were the performers of religious ceremonies. Despite the fact that Kshatriyas were the next class after Brahmins, they had a high position in society, the state, military power, and material wealth were all in the hands of Kshatriyas. Vaishyas formed the main part of the society. They were mainly herdsmen and farmers who supplied the necessary material wealth to the Brahmins and Kshatriyas. The first three varnas - Brahmins, Kshatriyas and Vaishyas - belong to the "twice born" category. Shudras were deprived of such a proud name. Shudras were usually poor, low-caste peasants and Malays. Although they were not slaves, they could fall into the position of slaves due to the necessity of the times. Thus, the destruction of the primitive community system led to the emergence of castes.

"History of casteism in India", in particular, from the ancient centuries to the 21st century, is devoted to the factor of religion in the social, economic, spiritual, and religious life of India and the reasons for the division of people into different

classes. Closely helps to introduce the main problems in India.

Causes of stratification: there are several that lead to the stratification of human society there are main reasons:

Gender inequality	Physical advantage	Access to resources	Economic benefits
Society has always been patriarchal or matriarchal, therefore for which one of the sexes prevailed and had certain privileges.	In primitive society, the strongest representatives of the tribe are the largest had rights. This division continued in more advanced civilizations. Until the Middle Ages, warriors were the most noble and privileged members of society	If someone initially has more resources, its in society the probability of getting a higher position is much higher	During the era of nation states, the dominant ethnic group usually had more opportunities to run businesses and participate in politics.

In short, social stratification is a stratification that occurs in any society. No one is trying to organize such a stratification. However, this inevitably occurs because everyone strives to get certain benefits, to have a higher position and to be more influential, as a result of which a certain hierarchy is formed and social inequality appears. Modern states are social seeks to minimize the impact of stratification on people's quality of life and to allow everyone equal access to social elevators.

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